

THE ART OF TRAGEDY IN THE LITERARY HERITAGE OF EDGAR ALLAN POE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17954232>

Abstract. *Edgar Allan Poe's contribution in the development of tragic mood in American literature is enormous. Especially his short story 'The Tell-Tale Heart' not only signals the start of psychological horror but also characterizes one of the most stylistic features in the examples of Gothic literature. This paper explores the issue of tragic life and fictional representation of the guilt and conscience in his short story "The Tell-Tale Heart" (1843). It demonstrates how Poe constructs tragic atmosphere through a unique combination of psychological depth, symbolic imagery, and stylistic precision.*

Key words: *Edgar Allan Poe, The Tell-Tale Heart, Gothic literature, madness, irrational fear, tragic mood, psychological horror, symbolic imagery.*

Introduction. The perception of tragedy plays a crucial role in world literature throughout centuries, evolving from classical interpretations of human torture to more psychological and symbolic representations in contemporary literary traditions. Among the writers who substantially changed the nature of literary tragedy is Edgar Allan Poe, a key figure in American Romanticism whose works remodeled the thematic and stylistic landscape of nineteenth-century literature.

His passion with darker sides of human consciousness – madness, guilt, fear and moral disintegration- enabled him to construct a distinct mode of tragic expression that differentiates from traditional notions rooted in fate and heroic collapse. Instead, Poe situates tragedy within the individual psyche, making psychological conflict the principal force of his narratives. 'The Tell-Tale Heart' is a story of a nameless person. He explains his being extremely nervous but not that he is insane. To prove that he is not insane, he shares an event from his past. He tells about an old man and that he loved him except his horrible eye.

Methodology and Literature Review. This research employs a qualitative, text-based analytical approach designed to explore how Edgar Allan Poe constructs tragic mood in his short story 'The Tell-Tale Heart'. Since the study pays attention to literary meaning, emotional atmosphere, and stylistic devices, qualitative methods are well-matched for showing the psychological and aesthetic complexity of the text. The study examines Poe's stylistic techniques –such as repetition, sound patterns, sentence rhythm, and point of view-through the lens of stylistics. Narratological tools, including focalization, narrative reliability, and temporal structure, are applied to understand how the narrator's voice shapes the emotional atmosphere of the story.

These methods highlight how narrative form and language operate together to produce a tragic effect. In the story Poe has utilized various things which carry symbolic significance. The Old man's Eye: The eye is a symbol of narrator's paranoia and insanity as there was no obvious reason to kill the old man. The narrator only wanted to get rid of the eye. "One of his eyes resembled that of a vulture."

The eye also indicates less visual clarity and simplicity of the old man, "...a pale blue eye, with a film over it" that he generally did not trust people. Eyes are the windows to the soul and the narrator describes it as the eye of a vulture. Vultures, which feed upon the dead, are always present and diligent and see everything, symbolizing penetration. He is frightened that the old man will see deep into his fears. Shamaila Amir intends to illustrate that the old man's eye in "The Tell-Tale Heart" serves as a main symbol representing the narrator's paranoia, psychological instability, and warped conception of reality.

Rather than presenting a rational incentive for murder, the text stresses that the narrator kills the old man only due to his fixation on the "vulture eye." This demonstrates that acts of aggression are rooted in biological and emotional impulses rather than calculated logic but by an obsessive and irrational fear, exposing the depth of his mental illness. The description of the eye as "pale blue, with a film over it" shows the old man's physical frailty and fragility, yet the narrator interprets it as destructive and pernicious. By calling it "the eye of a vulture," a bird associated with death, decay, and predatory watching, the narrator projects his own inner fears onto the old man. The eye becomes a metaphor for the narrator's terror that someone might "see" into his mind and reveal the guilt, madness, or secrets he is hiding. Thus, the author argues that the eye symbolizes penetration, exposure, and the narrator's fear of being psychologically uncovered.

Results and Discussions. An analysis of "The Tell-Tale Heart" by Edgar Allan Poe shows that the story's tragic mood is created by a blend of inner psychological turmoil, symbolic elements, and heightened writing style. The data illustrates that tragedy in his short story does not arise from external occasions or social affairs, but rather from the narrator's intimate collapse and the destructive motive of his mind. Poe's form of tragedy is psychological in nature, expressing the downfall of a character whose fear, guilt, and obsession ultimately consume him. One of the most indispensable results of the study is main role of the old man's eye as a symbol of the narrator's paranoia and mental instability. As the analysis indicates, the narrator's obsession with 'vulture eye' is irrational and disconnected from reality, showing that his tragic failure is rooted in an internalized fear rather than a verified danger.

The narrator's hidden fears are shown through their intense focus on the eye. This symbolic object triggers the narrator's descent into madness, indicating how Poe utilizes plain physical details to evoke substantial psychological tragedy. The discussion also remarks Poe's mastery of stylistic techniques that intensify tragic mood. Through repetition, rhythmic sentence patterns, and abrupt tonal shifts, Poe expresses the unstable mental state of the narrator. These stylistic elements create an atmosphere of growing unease, revealing how tragedy progresses slowly- moving from a low level of generalized anxiety to a state of acute psychosis.

The use of first-person narration further deepens the tragic effect, as the reader undergoes the narrator's fear, obsession, and guilt from within his consciousness. This narrative technique provides that the reader witnesses the tragic decrease not as an external occasion, but as an intimate psychological journey.

Conclusion. The results of the analysis illustrate that "The Tell-Tale Heart" is a profound example of psychological tragedy. Through symbols such as the eye and heartbeat, through stylistic precision, and through a deep portrayal of guilt and madness, Poe creates an innovative form of tragic mood that keeps on influencing contemporary literature.

Dekabr, 2025-Yil

The story demonstrates that the most powerful tragedies are those that emerge from within the human psyche, making Poe's work a significant contribution to the evolution of tragic aesthetics.

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